

G E O F I T[®]
SMART GEOTHERMAL

**Cost-effective enhanced geothermal
systems for energy efficient building
retrofitting**

<http://geofit-project.eu/>

Co-funded by the
European Union

H2020 GEOFIT Project

GEOFIT is an EU-funded innovation project aiming to develop and deploy cost-effective enhanced geothermal systems on energy efficient building retrofitting.

Challenges

The building sector is responsible for the 40% of the total energy consumption and represents about a third of Europe's CO2 emissions. Heating and cooling account for 50% of this annual energy consumption and almost half of EU buildings have boilers installed before 1992, with an efficiency rate of below 60%. Moreover, refurbishment rate for energy renovation of existing buildings is currently below 1%.

EUROPEAN TARGETS FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND RENEWABLE ENERGY THEREFORE CALL FOR STRONG IMPROVEMENTS OF EXISTING BUILDINGS.

Opportunity

Shallow geothermal has a great potential in Europe, but its adoption is hindered by long installation time and cost, technical difficulty in coupling heat pumps with existing high temperature heating systems, and the risk of structural damages or disruption caused by drilling activities.

GEOFIT is an integrated industrially driven action, funded by the H2020 programme and carried out by 24 partners across EU, aimed at deployment of cost effective enhanced geothermal systems (EGS) on energy efficient building retrofitting.

This entails the technical development of innovative EGS and its components, namely non-standard heat exchanger configurations, a novel hybrid heat pump and electrically driven compression heat pump systems and set of heating and cooling components to be integrated with the novel GSHP concepts, all specially designed to be applied in energy efficient retrofitting projects.

To make viable the novel EGS in energy efficient building retrofitting, a suite of tools and technologies is developed, including: low invasive risk assessment technologies, site-inspection and worksite building monitoring techniques (SHM), control systems for cost-effective and optimized EGS in operation phase and novel Building Information Modeling (BIM) tools for management of geothermal based retrofitting works (GEOBIM platform).

Furthermore, the project is committed with the application of novel drilling techniques as the improved low invasive vertical drilling and trenchless technologies.

OUR RESPONSE

GEOFIT solution

Efficient geothermal

GEOFIT will develop a holistic and novel approach to geothermal retrofitting which is cost-competitive, easy to install and capable to provide high temperature heating and safe.

As retrofitting is a complex and global process in which decisions cannot be made in isolation, it is necessary to devise an enhanced methodology, supported by an appropriate set of new tools and concepts for retrofitting that will fulfill the occupant's comfort needs, while achieving substantial reductions in energy consumption.

Therefore, GEOFIT has the following **objectives**:

- 1** The development of **innovative EGS systems, specifically developed for geothermal based retrofitting**, including the optimization and integration of the EGS' components: novel heat exchangers concepts, cost effective heat pumps, a set of novel heating and cooling components (low-temperature heating technology -LTH- and high temperature cooling technology - HTC-) and advanced IT control and monitoring technologies.
- 2** Deploy and integrate advanced methods of worksite inspection, ground research, building structural monitoring, TRT drilling and worksite characterization into **advanced geothermal based retrofitting methods based on multi-stakeholder and collaborative approach** based mainly on IDP (integrated delivery project) and IDDS (integrated design and delivery solutions) methods.
- 3** The implementation of a **global, effective, energy-efficient retrofitting strategy for the stock of existing buildings in Europe**, targeting a ROI between 5 to 6 years boosting the adoption of appropriate geothermal based energy-efficient building retrofitting technologies and methods.

INNOVATION

Tools & methods

Novel technologies

SHALLOW-EARTH HEAT EXCHANGER CONCEPTS COUPLED TO INNOVATIVE DRILLING TECHNIQUES

GEOFIT will develop advanced modeling tools and innovative techniques and technological components for enhanced, easy-to-install and economical geothermal systems.

NOVEL TECHNOLOGIES AND INTEGRATED SYSTEM CONCEPTS DELIVERING ULTRA EFFICIENT HEATING AND COOLING SOLUTIONS

GEOHERMAL SYSTEMS AS FLEXIBLE ASSETS, BIM AT THE BUILDING LEVEL AND LINKED INTO BIM AT THE CITY INFORMATION MODELLING LEVEL

GROUND PENETRATING RADAR AND STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING TO REDUCE RISK

AMBITION

Optimal system integration

The challenge facing the project goes beyond drilling, GEOFIT will offer innovative heating/cooling systems and heat pumps that are suitable for floor heating to achieve maximum energy savings, thermal comfort, etc. Our goal is optimal system integration.

Energy savings

Operative temperature, °C

Thermal comfort

GEOFIT will develop a complete set of geothermal retrofitting project management tool-chains in:

- Retrofitting operations and integrated management framework (IDDS)
- ICT Tools for ground research and worksite monitoring
- BIM enabled methods and tools for geothermal based retrofitting

DEMONSTRATION

Pilot sites

Galway Demo Site

Sports center
IRELAND

5 pilot sites in 4 EU countries, with different building types and different soil conditions.

Aran Islands Demo Site

Residential
IRELAND

Talence Demo Site

Office space
FRANCE

Historical building
ITALY

Perugia Demo Site

San Cugat Demo Site

Primary school
SPAIN

The demonstration sites will be open case studies representing different climates and situations found throughout Europe.

Want to know more?

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER

The GEOFIT project publishes a yearly newsletter to announce events and report on progress. Subscribe here to stay informed!
<http://geofit-project.eu/project/newsletter/>

CONTACT US

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Consortium partners

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